

JOHASAM: Journal of Health, Applied Sciences and Management
Volume 5, Issue 2, November, 2021
ISSN: 1597-7085, ISSN (Online): 2756-5343

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5734419

Volume 5 | Issue 2 | 2021

HAND HYGIENE BEHAVIOURAL CHANGE AMID COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN YENAGOA, NIGERIA

**Odafivwotu Ohwo
Alexander R. Bekeowei**

Department of Geography and Environmental Management,
Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Nigeria

Abstract

It has been widely recognized that adequate hand hygiene behaviour is a simple and cost-effective measure for moderating the spread of covid-19. Hence, this study focused on hand hygiene behavioural change amid the COVID-19 pandemic in Yenagoa. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey design, which involved the administration of a set of questionnaires to 400 randomly selected respondents using the multi-stage sampling technique, and physical inspection of household's hygiene facilities. The findings revealed that amid the COVID-19, there was a marginal increase in the status of water supply and hygiene services from the initial levels before the pandemic. The t-test statistic revealed that there was a significant difference in the frequency of hand washing before and amid the COVID-19 pandemic. This means that the level of hand hygiene behaviour among the people increased significantly during the pandemic. However, much still need to be done as a reasonable proportion of the population in Yenagoa do not practice regular hand hygiene due to some identified constraints. It is therefore recommended, that government should provide water and hygiene services for the people and carry out mass education and aggressive campaigns on the need for regular hand hygiene by all..

© 2021 Rivers State College of Health Science & Management Technology
<https://www.rschst.edu.ng/journals/>